

Development of a Low-Cost Fully Functional Bioprinter

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Note: This is an early-stage preprint. The current PDF includes general photographs of the structure (internal and external views) and preliminary testing results; however, detailed visual materials of specific components and the full testing data for the bioprinted scaffolds are currently unavailable and will be included in subsequent updates.

Bioprinting technologies finds applications in various tissue engineering fields. However, industrial bioprinter models are prohibitively expensive. Existing DIY bioprinters necessitate placement in a laminar flow hood during bioprinting. However, available laminar flow hoods on the market also come at a relatively high cost. Therefore, this paper presents a self-contained bioprinter design based on the Tronxy x5sa plastic printer with sterility preservation capabilities. In addition, we introduce a versatile extruder design built on aluminum profiles and other readily available and affordable components, which can be installed on other models of most plastic printers without specialized technical skills. The printed parts are designed to leverage the unique characteristics of additive manufacturing printing technology. Together, we present a step-by-step guide with complete assembly and installation diagrams, and provide results verifying print quality.

Introduction

Bioprint finds applications in various tissue engineering fields. However, industrial bioprinter models are prohibitively expensive. In 2015, Hinton, T. J. et al. [1] developed the FRESH bioprinting method, later modified to FRESH 2.0 [2]. This method enabled the successful use of medical syringes as the basis for the extruder for creating complex printed forms using DIY bioprinter models. Using this method, researchers from Carnegie Mellon University printed a full-size heart model [3] utilizing a DIY printer developed by Adam Feinberg and colleagues [4]. Currently, a multitude of DIY bioprinter variations exist, broadly categorized based on the extruder type employed in their design: linear shaft-based movement [5-10], gear-based motion transmission [11-15], unique (with the ability to utilize additive

printing for construction) rail-based [16-19], tube-based material delivery [20-29], electro-motive force-based material delivery [30-31], multi-nozzle designs [32-38], using multiple stepper motors to drive the piston [39], as well as combination-type extruders [41]. However, the need for a design incorporating a sealed enclosure remains. Therefore, this paper proposes a bioprinter design enabling printing under sealed conditions with prior workspace decontamination, utilizing precise assembly technology for an extruder boasting lightweight construction and strength without adhesive bonds. Furthermore, the additive printed components in this work are designed considering the strength reserve of PLA plastic as well as the specific features of the additive printing technology itself.

Results

Each sample was printed using the Freeform Reversible Embedding of Suspended Hydrogels (FRESH) method [1,2] with 1% alginate bioink. The alginate was pre-sterilized by autoclaving prior to printing.

Printing of the Human Auricular Cartilage

Figure 1 presents a visual comparison between the virtual model of the auricular cartilage and its bioprinted counterpart. The sample was printed horizontally into a Petri dish secured with magnetic mounts. Printing was performed using a 2.5 ml Luer-lock syringe equipped with a 25G needle (1/2 inch length). The printing surface was cooled to a temperature of 16°C.

Figure 1. (1a) – printed sample; (1b) – virtual model.

Printing of the Vascular Scaffold Geometry

Figure 2 presents a visual comparison between the virtual model of the vascular structure and its printed counterpart. The sample was printed vertically into a specimen collection container secured with magnetic mounts. Printing was performed using a 2.5 ml Luer-lock syringe with a needle featuring an internal diameter of 0.6 mm and a length equal to the height of the vessel (approximately 40 mm). The printing surface was cooled to a temperature of 16°C.

Figure 2. (2a) – top view of the printed sample; (2b) – side view (horizontal) of the printed sample; (2c) – virtual model with dimensions.

The resulting sample was subsequently used for testing in a bioreactor [42]. To ensure compatibility with the dimensions of the bioreactor's working chamber, the length of the vessel sample was adjusted to match the calibrated parameters of the device.

Discussion

In this work, we developed an autonomous bioprinter based on the Tronxy X5SA Pro. The design was engineered to meet requirements for airtightness and autonomy. Sterilization of the workspace was performed via prolonged ozonation within a sealed environment using a UV lamp. The alginate was sterilized by autoclaving, which resulted in a degradation of the printed structures' geometry.

Methods

Enclosure

To ensure structural reliability while maintaining cost-effectiveness, the framework utilizes square aluminum profiles joined together with plastic corner brackets. These plastic corner connections are further reinforced with steel corner brackets. This design allows for perforation of holes at desired locations for mounting external elements using threaded rivets and routing electrical wiring within the profiles themselves, resulting in a sealed enclosure with the ability to install electronic control elements on the exterior of the housing. A photograph of the complete bioprinter assembly is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. A photograph of the complete bioprinter assembly, showing both external (left) and internal (right) views.

The data and power channels are routed internally within the profiles, located on the opposite side of the bioprinter from the power lines, to eliminate interference from the power lines.

Two layers of steel sheet are mounted onto the aluminum frame, with a layer of thermal insulation material and internal electronic wiring situated between them. For added reliability and sealing, the interior layer is reinforced by overlapping steel strips onto it.

The door is designed using a similar principle to the walls. Rubber gaskets serve as seals and are mounted on the door through threaded connections, avoiding the use of adhesive bonds due to their cytotoxicity and unreliability over time. The door itself is secured using tension locks, which, combined with the rubber gaskets, ensures a reliable seal between the door and the enclosure.

The Tronxy x5sa printer housing is located inside the enclosure. This printer acts as the base for the extruder's motion system due to its budget-friendly nature and simplicity of the required design. The Tronxy x5sa printer's printing table movement only occurs along the Z axis during printing. Since a considerable number of heavy components are mounted beneath the printing surface, this would negatively impact the printing process if the printing table moved along the Y axis during printing, as in the kinematics of printers like the Prusa or Printbot Simple. The bottom part of the Tronxy x5sa printer is overlaid onto the steel brackets and secured with screws through them, providing stability for the positioning of the aluminum profiles of the Tronxy x5sa housing. For even greater stability, the aluminum profiles of the Tronxy x5sa housing are fixed on each side from above and below with nylon and metal ties secured to the enclosure. This reinforced attachment of the Tronxy x5sa housing within the enclosure helps to mitigate any play that could occur during printing due to the heavier extruder design compared to the original factory-designed extruder, intended for printing with plastic.

Electronics

The main electronic components have been replaced with a combination of the Arduino Mega 2560 control board and a Smart full-graphic LSD monitor interface, due to their popularity and wide availability on the market. For ease and safety of use, the control monitor is mounted on the top of the exterior of the enclosure via an extended ribbon cable running through the enclosure following the principle described above. The control board and its connected components are enclosed in an insulating plastic housing, which is equipped

with a cooling system consisting of 40x40 mm fans to mitigate overheating of the electronic components inside.

For clear visibility of the workspace, cameras are installed with connecting cables routed outside the enclosure. A lighting fixture is also incorporated, featuring two fluorescent lamps that are individually switched using an external switch: a daylight lamp to provide visibility when the door is closed; and an ultraviolet lamp for pre-sterilization of the workspace.

All of the aforementioned devices are powered by an internal distributor, consisting of 220V and 12V wires routed from an external power supply into the enclosure using the principle described above

Extruder

The extruder is based on an aluminum profile. This decision was made to allow for easy installation of this extruder on other models of plastic printers if necessary, without requiring specialized technical skills.

To reduce weight and ensure smooth piston movement, commonly available MGN[41]-type rails with carriages are used as linear guides for the piston. Due to its size, this rail is tightly mounted into the central groove of the aluminum profile using dowels and screws. This allows for smooth carriage movement by ensuring that the rail is aligned with the profile groove during assembly. Most of the remaining parts of the extruder are made of plastic using printing to lighten the design. The plastic parts are designed to be mounted, just like the rail, tightly to the profile and to each other using threaded connections, ensuring precise installation and, consequently, alignment of the piston movement during printing.

The syringe used in the extruder as a nozzle is secured on each axis by replaceable mounts. The size of these mounts can be adjusted depending on the caliber of the installed syringe by modifying the dimensions of the required parts of the original STL file of the model. To ensure both forward and backward movement of the piston, the syringe piston is also secured with a replaceable mount.

Print Surface

The print surface consists of a steel sheet, on top of which magnets are placed to securely hold any necessary container with a supporting solution.

Beneath the steel sheet of the print surface is a cooling system based on a Peltier element. From below, the Peltier element is tightly mounted to the

bottom aluminum base with a threaded connection, with the cold side facing upwards. The Peltier element is pressed from below by the cooling element of the liquid cooling system. Current supply to the Peltier element is controlled by an electronic thermostat, which breaks the electrical circuit supplying the element when the set temperature, read by a thermistor attached to the print table, is reached.

On top of the bottom aluminum base with holes located at the points where the screw heads protrude, there is a copper sheet, which receives heat from the bottom aluminum sheet and, in turn, receives heat from the upper working steel sheet. In this case, thermal paste is applied between the sheets for optimal heat transfer. Heat from the liquid cooling system is removed outside the housing by an exhaust system consisting of a plastic housing for the fans that remove heat from the radiator of the liquid cooling system and an air duct that directs the extracted hot airflow through an external fan to the outside.

The liquid cooling system itself is powered by an additional power supply unit mounted inside the working space, while the Peltier element and its electronic controller are powered by the distributor described earlier.

Air system

Air is supplied into the workspace through an air supply filtration system, which consists of: a plastic base, a 120x120mm external fan that directs airflow into the workspace; an air filter that allows external airflow to pass into the workspace; and an internal fan that distributes the incoming airflow from the filter into the workspace. The air is exhausted through a duplicated exhaust air system on both sides, consisting of a plastic base secured to the enclosure through soft seals, on which a 120x120mm fan is mounted, as well as a plastic plug, used when there is no need to utilize this exhaust air flow system.

Device Components

The frame utilizes 30x30x1.5 mm square aluminum profiles. The frame dimensions are 1090x750x640mm. The aluminum profiles are connected using Joker-type plastic connectors. The soft wall seals 3*30 mm are made of polyethylene foam, laid in two intersecting layers. The wall material is 0.35 mm thick galvanized steel. The plates for securing the steel sheets are made of 40x4 mm hot-rolled steel. The door seal is made of rubber and has dimensions of 11.3x9.5mm. The Arduino Mega 2560 serves as the electronic

control board, along with the Ramps 1.4 shield connected to it, featuring A4988 drivers and NEMA17 stepper motors. The power supply unit has parameters of 12V 30A 360W. The internal lighting source is the FTD-202 fluorescent lamp. The liquid cooling system is Alseye H360. The Peltier element is TEC1-12715 SR. The thermostat is a W1209 12V thermostat relay. The thermal paste has parameters of 0.7 W/mK. The rotational speed of the air supply system fans is controlled by a 12-40V 10A PWM speed controller. The air filter is based on a 6mm thick F5 fine air filtration material. MGN9H-type rail with carriage for the extruder.

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